

Volatile organic compounds (VOCs) and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) in indoor spaces – a review and meta-analysis of field measurements in Europe

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Abstract

Indoor air quality is a significant aspect of public health, yet it remains less studied than outdoor air pollution. Understudied indoor pollutants include volatile organic compounds (VOCs) and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs). This review and meta-analysis focus on these two groups of compounds that are known for their potential health effects, including respiratory issues, neurological disorders, and carcinogenicity. This study synthesizes data from field measurements in various indoor environments, including residential homes, offices, and schools, over the last two decades in Europe. Meta-analytic techniques were used to determine the overall concentration ranges and to identify patterns and trends in the pollutants. Our findings reveal that VOC and PAH concentrations vary widely depending on the indoor setting and region. The most common sources identified include tobacco smoke, cooking emissions, heating systems, and certain building materials such as paints and varnishes. The results also show significant seasonal variation, with higher concentrations typically observed in the colder months due to increased indoor activity and reduced ventilation. This the need for improved indoor air quality management practices and regulatory standards to minimize the health risks associated with VOCs and PAHs. This review of 46 scientific publications aims to inform future studies, and guide future field measurements and risk assessments in epidemiological studies by providing a detailed overview of the current state of knowledge and identifying research gaps.

1. Introduction

According to the European Environment Agency, air pollution is the most important environmental health risk affecting millions of people (European Environment Agency, 2023). Although a great body of evidence for the ambient air pollution health effects exists, indoor air quality (IAQ) could also be regarded as a critical aspect of environmental health. Individuals spend a significant amount of their time indoors, particularly in developed urban settings where the majority of the population lives, thus increasing the exposure to indoor air pollutants that account for more than 3 million deaths annually (World Health Organization, 2023). While efforts have been made to mitigate ambient air pollution, IAQ remains a concern due to the presence of various pollutants, including particulate matter (PM), volatile organic compounds (VOCs), and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs). VOCs and PAHs are of particular interest due to their different sources and their potentially adverse effects on macromolecules (Kazensky et al., 2024). Many studies have addressed these pollutants individually, however a systematic review and meta-analysis is needed to synthesise existing findings, identify knowledge gaps and guide future research and policy efforts. This review provides a comprehensive overview of the current evidence on VOCs and PAHs in indoor air. It examines their sources, distribution, levels in various indoor environments, and their potential health effects. Additionally, a meta-analysis of existing studies quantifies the overall levels of these pollutants and assesses regional or temporal trends. Ultimately, this review aims to contribute to efforts to promote a healthier indoor environment and protect public health.

PAHs stand out as a significant group of air pollutants that impact human health. Their association with adverse health outcomes, including mutagenesis and carcinogenesis, underscores their potency in the development of chronic diseases and their involvement in increased morbidity and mortality in certain susceptible populations (Kim et al., 2013; Masiol et al., 2012; Stading et al., 2021; Verma et al., 2021). While individual PAH concentrations might not lead to immediate health effects, their mixtures can create additive, synergistic or potentiating toxic effects (Engraff et al., 2011; Nováková et al., 2020; Olsson et al., 2010). Exposure to PAHs has been associated with adverse health outcomes, respiratory and cardiovascular diseases, cancer, and developmental abnormalities (L. Yang et al., 2021). The mechanism underlying PAHs toxicity involve DNA damage, oxidative stress induction, gene expression alterations, and epigenetic changes, all of which contribute to chronic disease development (Peng et al., 2023; Xiao et al., 2023). Of particular concern is the chronic exposure and persistent nature of PAHs in the human body, which further exacerbates the health implications (Boffetta et al., 1997). PAHs can enter indoor spaces through various pathways. Their primary source is the incomplete combustion of organic materials such as fuels, coal, gas, wood, and oil (Dat & Chang, 2017; Kumar et al., 2016; Marchand et al., 2004; Patel et al., 2020; Ravindra et al., 2008). Other contributing sources may include cigarette smoke, cooking processes, and the use of certain building materials and consumer products (Bai & Li, 2022; M. Wang et al., 2021). Understanding the impact and sources on indoor air quality and their adverse effects on human health is crucial for effective emission reduction strategies. The presence of PAHs in various environmental matrices, such as air, water, soil, and food, underscores the global significance of their impact on public health.

VOCs are another significant group of air pollutants that considerably impact IAQ and human health. Despite the extensive research on VOCs, the relationship between individual indoor VOC concentrations and health outcomes remains insufficiently understood. Consequently, there are currently no universal health-based guideline values for VOCs in Europe. They are characterized by their high vapor pressure, which allows them to readily evaporate into the air at room temperature (Liu et al., 2021; World Health Organization (WHO), 2010). Exposure to VOCs in indoor environments is of concern due to their association with adverse health effects. Several studies have linked VOC exposure to respiratory issues,

allergic reactions, and other severe health outcomes, including neurodegenerative conditions (C. Li et al., 2020; Vardoulakis et al., 2020; Zheng et al., 2022), and cancer development, further emphasizing the importance of understanding and mitigating their presence in indoor air (Weschler & Nazaroff, 2008; Xiong et al., 2021). Various sources contribute to the presence of VOCs in indoor spaces, including building materials, furniture, cleaning items, personal care products, and activities such as cooking and smoking (Harčárová et al., 2020; H. Wang et al., 2022; Weschler & Nazaroff, 2008). Additionally, VOCs can originate from outdoor sources, such as vehicle emissions, industrial processes, and ambient air pollution, which can infiltrate indoor environments (Duan et al., 2023; X.-B. Li et al., 2022; Mohd Hanif et al., 2021). Chemical transformations and reactions occurring indoors can significantly affect the levels and composition of VOCs, leading to potential health risks (Abbatt & Wang, 2020). This review aims to provide a comprehensive overview of the behaviour, sources, exposure pathways, and health implications of VOCs in indoor environments. By synthesizing research findings, we will explore the impact of VOCs on indoor air quality and human health. Additionally, strategies for measuring, monitoring, and controlling VOC levels in indoor settings will be discussed.

The aim of the systematic review is to understand the sources, concentration levels and routes of exposure of indoor air pollutants, which is also the main goal of the Horizon EU EDIAQI (Evidence driven indoor air quality improvement, <https://ediaqi.eu/>) project (GA number 101057497). This will help validate the user-friendly IAQ monitoring solutions proposed by the EDIAQI project and contribute to establishing standardized guidelines for improving IAQ. Ultimately, this review will support policy makers in revising IAQ standards and implementing effective regulatory measures.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Search strategy and selection criteria

For this meta-analysis, a systematic search of the PubMed base was performed, including all relevant studies from 1st January 2010 till 1st April 2024 related to indoor measurements and health effects of PAHs and VOCs. The full search strategy is described in the Supplementary materials. The main search criteria involved scanning all publications (title/abstract) with several keywords: Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons OR PAH OR PAHs OR Volatile Organic Compounds OR VOC OR VOCs AND indoor (or school, schools, office, offices, etc.) AND exposure, OR monitoring OR measurements, etc. The initial results contained 4225 papers. Limiting the review period to 2010-2024 reduced the results to 3101 publications. Applying the "free full text" filter further narrowed the results to 1276 publications. Abstracts of these 1276 papers were extracted using Python and stored in a designated folder. Each abstract was then manually reviewed to determine if it included the necessary measurements for the meta-analysis. Additionally, only studies conducted within the European Union were considered, as this area was the focus of the review. The diagram of the systematic search process and the included studies is presented in Figure 1. A total of 46 studies were included in the further analysis.

Figure 1. The diagram of the systematic search process and the included studies based on the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) protocol (Moher et al., 2009)

3. Results and discussion

After thoroughly reviewing the abstracts of papers that met the search criteria, 46 papers were selected which fit the specified requirements (Figure 2). Of these, 24 and 25 focus on indoor measurements of PAHs and VOCs respectively in Europe. Some papers cover measurements of both PAHs and VOCs, which is why the total number of studies across different environments does not match the overall number of selected studies. Within the VOC papers, the studies are divided into measured of concentrations in the air in offices, homes, and schools: three papers on offices, ten on homes, and twelve on schools. For PAHs, the division is as follows: nine papers on dust-bound PAHs, six on PM-bound PAHs in air in homes, and nine on PM-bound PAHs in the air in schools.

Figure 2. Map with the number of studies per country in the European Union included in the review

As illustrated in the map (Figure 2), most studies are concentrated in the southern regions of the European Union what is in line with the EEA’s report on European air quality (Horálek et al., 2023). Notably, Italy has the highest number of studies with ten, followed by Portugal with eight studies, and Poland and Spain with five and four studies, respectively. A limitation might be that the needed data quality looked for during the search was a limiting factor and could drive a bias towards such a geographical distribution. In the following subsection, the individual categories (offices, homes, schools, and dust-bound) of indoor spaces will be assessed for either/or PAHs and VOCs.

3.1. VOCs in indoor spaces

Within the VOC papers, the studies are divided into measured concentrations in offices, homes, and schools: three papers on offices, ten on homes, and twelve on schools (Table S1). The most commonly measured VOCs in these studies were benzene, toluene, ethylbenzene, formaldehyde, styrene, and xylenes. These compounds were chosen due to their prevalence and potential health impacts in indoor environments, providing a comprehensive overview of VOC exposure in different settings. The table with mean VOC concentrations in households, schools and offices and total volatile organic compounds (TVOC) concentrations in different indoor environments can be found in Supplementary material (Table S1), and the average VOCs concentrations are shown as figures in the following subsections.

3.1.1. VOC concentrations in offices

This section presents the findings from studies investigating VOC levels in office environments. Figure 3 summarizes the results of three studies that measured the concentrations of various VOCs in office settings. Five common VOCs identified in all three studies were selected: benzene, toluene, ethylbenzene, *m,p*-xylene, and *o*-xylene. These VOCs are among the most commonly measured in indoor spaces. The results compare the average concentrations of these common VOCs in three different office environments in Italy, France, and Poland. Benzene concentrations varied across the studies, with the highest level recorded in the study by Gallon et al. (Gallon et al., 2020) at $6.12 \pm 10.09 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ and the lowest concentration recorded in

the study by Kozielska et al. (Kozielska et al., 2020) at $1.15 \pm 0.99 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. Toluene concentrations also varied significantly, with the highest concentration reported at $12.73 \pm 4.35 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ and the lowest concentration $4.01 \pm 2.15 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. The levels of ethylbenzene were relatively low across all studies, with the highest being $2.00 \pm 0.96 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ and the lowest $0.63 \pm 0.16 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ in Kozielska et al. Gallon et al. reported the highest *m,p*-xylene concentration at $8.03 \pm 2.50 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, while Kozielska et al. reported the lowest at $0.53 \pm 0.15 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. Concentrations of *o*-xylene ranged from $1.47 \pm 0.52 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ in Fuselli et al. (Fuselli et al., 2010) to $3.68 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ in Gallon et al., with Kozielska et al. reporting $1.18 \pm 0.48 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$.

Figure 3. The mean volatile organic compounds (VOC) concentrations quantified in office environments ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) from reviewed papers.

These findings illustrate the variability in VOC concentrations in office environments depending on the location, the specific VOCs measured, and possibly also the measurement methods (given in the Supplement). The differences in VOC levels can be attributed to various factors such as building materials, office equipment, ventilation systems, and indoor activities, such as different phases of the construction process as well as materials and solvents used for furnishing (Gallon et al., 2020). The study by Gallon et al. differs from the other two studies (Figure 3) as it was conducted during the construction process of an office building. This specific context likely contributed to the higher concentrations of certain VOCs observed in this study. The elevated levels of benzene and other VOCs such as *m,p*-xylene ($8.03 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) can be attributed to emissions from construction materials, adhesives, paints, and solvents used during the building process (Gallon et al., 2020). This finding was also reported by Liang et al. (2014) in a study from China, where similar results were observed. In contrast, the studies by Fuselli et al. and Kozielska et al. measured VOC levels in fully operational office environments, where the primary sources of VOCs are typically furniture, office equipment, and cleaning products rather than construction materials. This difference in context explains why the TVOC levels in Gallon et al. ($23.8 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) are higher compared to Fuselli et al. ($22.17 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) and Kozielska et al. ($14.33 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$). These findings highlight the importance of considering the building phase and activities when assessing indoor air quality and indicate the need for appropriate ventilation and mitigation strategies during and after construction to protect IAQ. The European project OFFICAIR (Mandin et al., 2017) aimed to broaden the existing knowledge regarding IAQ in modern office buildings. Thirty-seven office buildings participated in the summer campaign (2012), and thirty-five participated in the winter campaign (2012–2013). Indoor concentration means ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) of VOCs monitored in office buildings during the OFFICAIR project were as follows: benzene at 1.4 ± 1.3 , toluene at 8.1 ± 8.5 , and ethylbenzene at 1.8 ± 2.0 during the summer, and benzene at 2.1 ± 1.7 , toluene at 6.1 ± 8.8 , and

ethylbenzene at 1.3 ± 1.2 during the winter. These concentrations also align with those measured in the studies discussed, suggesting that standardizing the measurement of specific VOCs could enhance the comparability of research findings.

3.1.2. VOC concentration in houses

Given the search criteria, ten studies were included in our data set in the section on measuring VOCs in homes/apartments. Many studies address different sets of VOCs when assessing concentrations in households. Four studies reported only TVOC concentrations, as shown in Table S1 in Supplementary materials. Salthammer has provided a critical assessment of TVOC (Salthammer, 2022), hence, we advise the reader to take this extensive study into account. In a study by Rodrigues Dos Santos et al. (Rodrigues Dos Santos et al., 2020) the highest TVOC concentration reported in Portugal was $3110 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ over a 2-year period. In contrast, Wallner et al. (Wallner et al., 2015) found a significantly lower concentration of $334.5 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ in Austria. Mečiarová et al. (Mečiarová et al., 2017) reported a concentration of $425 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ in Slovakia, which is higher than in Austria but much lower than in Portugal. Pietrogrande et al. (Pietrogrande et al., 2021) measured a concentration of 348.6 ppb in Italy, which is considerably higher than those in Austria and Slovakia but lower than in Portugal when expressed in $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. Within the remaining six studies, the concentrations of individual VOCs were measured in indoor household environments. Figure S1 in the Supplementary material shows the number of individual VOCs measured per study. Martins et al. measured 10 VOCs, Ninyà et al. measured 15 VOCs, Rosch et al. measured 50, Alves et al. 20, Alvarez-Vaca et al. 30, and Yang et al. measured 25 VOCs. In the following text, only the most common VOCs will be presented. Due to the significant variation in the number of VOCs measured across these studies, the five most commonly measured VOCs are presented in Table S1 in the Supplementary material. In the study by Martins et al. (Martins et al., 2012) conducted in Portugal, VOC concentrations were notably the highest among all reviewed papers, with values of $4.53 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ for benzene, $23.93 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ for toluene, $7.68 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ for ethylbenzene, and $14.6 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ for formaldehyde (Figure 4). The aim of this research was to evaluate the relationship between total air pollution exposure and airway changes in 51 wheezing children. The study found significant associations between increased exposure to pollutants like PM_{10} , NO_2 , benzene, toluene, and ethylbenzene and adverse respiratory outcomes. These findings underscore the impact of VOCs on respiratory health, particularly in vulnerable populations such as children. Toluene is the dominant VOC in several studies, with Martins et al. in Portugal and Yang et al. (S. Yang et al., 2020) in Switzerland showing the highest mean concentrations at 23.93 and $28 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, respectively. Formaldehyde levels are also among the highest, with Ninyà et al. (Ninyà et al., 2022) in Spain reporting $10.15 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. Rösch et al. (Rösch et al., 2014) in Germany recorded a notable concentration of $13.18 \pm 16.91 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ of toluene and a lower level of styrene at $0.83 \pm 1.9 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. Similarly, Alves et al. (Alves et al., 2020) in Portugal and Alvarez-Vaca et al. (Alvarez-Vaca et al., 2022) in Luxembourg reported moderate levels of benzene and formaldehyde.

Figure 4. The mean volatile organic compounds (VOC) concentrations quantified in houses ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) from reviewed papers

Ninyà et al. (Ninyà et al., 2022) monitored VOCs and semi-VOCs in homes and school settings in Tarragona, Spain, and found that the concentrations of solvents were significantly higher indoors than outdoors, particularly due to anti-COVID-19 measures. Rösch et al. conducted a large-scale study in Leipzig, Germany, identifying various sources and patterns of VOCs in homes. They found that IAQ was influenced by ventilation, human activities, furnishings, and natural processes. Alves et al. studied VOCs in kitchens and found that indoor sources significantly contributed to overall VOC levels, with variations depending on the type of cooking appliances used. Alvarez-Vaca et al. (Alvarez-Vaca et al., 2022) analysed VOC levels in Luxembourg households, identifying health risks associated with certain VOCs and emphasizing the need for a national indoor pollution surveillance system. Finally, Yang et al. (S. Yang et al., 2020) examined VOC concentrations in energy-efficient dwellings in Switzerland, finding that energy renovation measures without adequate ventilation could lead to higher levels of indoor pollutants.

3.1.3. VOC concentration in schools

In this section, 13 studies were selected for comparison on measuring VOCs in schools (Table S1 in Supplementary materials). The challenges associated with different VOC measurements remain consistent with those previously described for offices and households, including differences in units of measurement, especially for total volatile organic compounds (TVOC) concentrations. Four studies reported only TVOC concentrations, as shown in Table S1.

In the study by Konstantinou et al. (2022), the median TVOC measured in primary schools was 2991.78 ppb, which is approximately $4240.18 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. Rufo et al. (2016) and Fuentes-Ferragud et al. (2024) reported TVOC concentrations of $170 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ and 0.08 ppm, while Ferriera and Cardoso (2013) reported TVOC concentrations of 94.04 ppm. In the remaining nine studies, individual VOCs concentrations were measured in school environments. Table S1 shows the concentration of the five common VOCs in these studies, which is graphically shown in Figure S2 in the Supplementary material. As can be seen, the concentrations of the same VOCs in different schools of different countries are similar, with two outliers for formaldehyde in Madureira et al. (Madureira et al., 2015) and Settimo et al. (Settimo et al., 2020). The high concentration of formaldehyde could be attributed to factors such as the presence of new building materials, furniture, or

high usage of formaldehyde-based products in the school environment during the time of the study. Additionally, poor ventilation systems can exacerbate the accumulation of formaldehyde indoors. Benzene concentrations are relatively low across all studies, with the highest values reported by Settimo et al. (2.17 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$). Toluene concentrations vary, with the highest values reported by Martins et al. (Martins et al., 2012) (20.68 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$), Madureira et al. (15.1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$), and Vornanen-Winqvist et al. (Vornanen-Winqvist et al., 2018) (16 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$). Marzocca et al. (Marzocca et al., 2017) and De Gennaro et al. (De Gennaro et al., 2013) reported the lowest concentration values of all VOCs compared to other studies. Xylenes show moderate variability, with Madureira et al. (21.6 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) reporting the highest concentration. Ethylbenzene has the highest values in Martins et al. and Ninyà et al. (Ninyà et al., 2022). Gibson et al. (Gibson et al., 2012) reported low VOC concentrations instead of formaldehyde, which was on average 12 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. The study by Raffy et al. (Raffy et al., 2017), only measured three infrequent VOCs: α -hexachlorocyclohexane (0.4 ng/m^3), γ -hexachlorocyclohexane (1 ng/m^3) and dichlorodiphenyltrichloroethane (1 ng/m^3), which were not measured in any of the other studies for comparison.

The studies on VOCs in school environments highlight significant variations in IAQ due to different sources and activities. Martins et al. evaluated the relationship between air pollution and airway changes in children, and found that increased exposure to VOCs like benzene, toluene, and ethylbenzene was associated with decreased lung function and increased airway inflammation. Ninyà et al. (Ninyà et al., 2022) monitored VOCs and semi-VOCs in a school in Tarragona, Spain, and noted that indoor concentrations were significantly higher than outdoor levels, mainly due to increased cleaning activities and the use of hydroalcoholic gels as part of anti-COVID-19 measures. Madureira et al. (Madureira et al., 2015) studied CO_2 , PM_{10} , and VOCs in naturally ventilated primary schools in Porto, Portugal, and identified that reduced ventilation and indoor activities were major contributors to indoor air pollution. Their study indicated that VOC levels were influenced by indoor sources, occupant behaviour, and maintenance activities. Vornanen-Winqvist et al. investigated the effects of a hybrid ventilation system on indoor air quality in a school building in Finland, and found that proper ventilation significantly reduced the concentrations of VOCs, particularly toluene, and improved perceived indoor air quality. Marzocca et al. (Marzocca et al., 2017) investigated a primary school in Taranto, Italy, near an industrial complex. They found that indoor VOC concentrations, particularly terpenes and 2-butoxyethanol, were significantly higher than outdoor levels, indicating strong indoor sources likely related to cleaning activities. Settimo et al. (Settimo et al., 2020) emphasized the importance of understanding the impact of students' activities on indoor air quality. The study highlighted that regular air exchange and modernization of school facilities are crucial for improving IAQ, especially given the high occupancy and diverse activities in schools. De Gennaro et al. (De Gennaro et al., 2013) monitored VOCs in eight naturally ventilated school buildings in Italy, and identified high concentrations of terpenes such as α -pinene and limonene indoors, with lower outdoor levels. Gibson et al. (Gibson et al., 2012) focused on libraries and archives, and found higher concentrations of acetic acid and furfural in locations with paper-based collections, suggesting these compounds as markers of cellulose degradation.

Figure 5. The mean VOC concentrations ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) quantified in different environments with error bars indicating standard deviations.

Figure 5 visualizes the concentrations of five VOCs — benzene, toluene, ethylbenzene, formaldehyde, and xylenes — across three different environments: schools, offices, and houses. The benzene concentration is relatively low across all environments, with minor variations. Concentrations are lower in schools and offices and slightly higher in houses. Toluene concentrations are highest in houses, followed by schools and offices. The high/large error bars indicate a significant variation in toluene concentrations, especially in houses. Ethylbenzene concentrations are relatively low across all environments, similar to benzene, with minimal differences. The measurement variation is also small, as indicated by the error bars. Formaldehyde shows a notably high concentration in schools, followed by offices and houses. The variation in formaldehyde concentrations is significant in all environments, particularly schools. Xylene concentrations are higher in houses, offices, and schools. The error bars show a moderate variation in xylene concentrations across different environments. The concentrations of toluene and formaldehyde were the highest among the measured VOCs, with considerable variability. This suggests that indoor air quality can differ greatly depending on the environment, influenced by factors such as building materials, ventilation systems, and indoor activities. High formaldehyde concentration in schools might be due to the use of specific materials or inadequate ventilation.

3.2. Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) in indoor spaces

Regarding the assessment of PAHs, the existing literature is divided into categories based on the environments studied (Table S2 in Supplementary material). A total of nine papers focuses on the concentrations of dust-bound PAHs, while six studies investigate the concentrations of PM-bound PAHs within residential homes, offering a detailed analysis of indoor air quality and potential exposure risks in domestic settings. Furthermore, nine papers address PM-bound PAH concentrations in school environments.

3.2.1. Dust-bound PAH concentrations in houses

Table S2 in Supplementary materials show the concentrations of various PAHs measured in dust-bound samples within indoor houses across different studies. The concentrations are given in two different units: pg/m^3 for Lim et al. (Lim et al., 2021) from Sweden and ng/g (nanograms per gram of dust) for the other studies. Lim et al. reported PAH concentrations such as benzo[a]pyrene (BaP) at $13.7 \text{ pg}/\text{m}^3$, benzo[a]anthracene (BaA) at $6.6 \text{ pg}/\text{m}^3$, and pyrene (Pyr) at $20.4 \text{ pg}/\text{m}^3$, with a total PAH concentration of $238.8 \text{ pg}/\text{m}^3$. In contrast, Fromme et al. (Fromme et al., 2004) from Germany reported PAH concentrations with BaP at $270 \text{ ng}/\text{g}$, BaA at $290 \text{ ng}/\text{g}$, and Pyr at $670 \text{ ng}/\text{g}$, giving a total of $6340 \text{ ng}/\text{g}$. Studies from Croatia (Jakovljević et al., 2022), Greece (Stamatelopoulou et al., 2021), Italy (Mannino & Orecchio, 2008), and the Czech Republic (Melymuk et al., 2016) also reported varying levels of PAHs in indoor dust. Notably, the Greek study by Besis et al. (Besis et al., 2021) presented an exceptionally high total PAH concentration of $4650 \text{ ng}/\text{g}$, as well as individual PAH concentrations. This diversity of PAH concentrations highlights the variability in indoor air pollution across different regions and methodologies, and the differences in units in the Lim et al. study indicates a need for careful unit standardization when comparing such data. Simonetti et al. (Simonetti et al., 2020) reported only total PAHs in two domestic environments were 417.2 and $5247.9 \text{ ng}/\text{g}$ in indoor dust, represented here as an average. The average concentrations of dust-bound PAHs in the five studies with the most available data and the same unit of measurement are shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Concentration of dust-bound polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) in households from reviewed papers.

Lim et al. conducted a study in preschools in Stockholm, Sweden, analysing PAHs in indoor dust and in PM in both indoor and ambient air. They identified vehicle emissions and biomass burning as significant sources of PAHs, with outdoor PM_{10} and indoor dust showing significant genotoxic potential despite relatively low PAH levels. Fromme et al. (Fromme et al., 2004) explored PAH concentrations in indoor and ambient air in Berlin residences, finding no significant differences between smoker and non-smoker apartments, with vehicular emissions identified as a primary source for non-smoker residences. Pieters et al. (Pieters et al., 2013) focused on the impact of PAHs on mitochondrial DNA content in house dust, and revealed that PAH exposure during winter is associated with mitochondrial damage, though no similar association was found during summer.

Jakovljević et al. (Jakovljević et al., 2022) provided the first data on PAH levels in Croatian households, finding lower PAH levels compared to global reports, but highlighting the elevated cancer risk for individuals exposed to the highest PAH concentrations, mainly from wood heating. Stamatelopoulou et al. (Stamatelopoulou et al., 2021) examined house dust in residences with young children in Athens, Greece, and found that PAHs and metals were the prevalent pollutants, with smoking, combustion processes, and traffic being significant contributors. The study concluded that the carcinogenic risk from PAHs was generally low, but ingestion of house dust posed the most important route of exposure to metals, particularly for children. Besis et al. (Besis et al., 2021) conducted the first comprehensive analysis of PAHs, polybrominated diphenyl ethers (PBDEs), polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs), and nitrated polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (NPAHs) in Greek house dust. The study revealed that PAHs had the highest median concentrations among the contaminants, but the health risk assessment indicated that the hazard index for all groups was below one, suggesting a low level of concern for both adults and children. Mannino et al. (Mannino & Orecchio, 2008) investigated PAH concentrations in indoor dust samples from the Palermo area in Italy. The study demonstrated a wide range of PAH concentrations, where the presence of smokers significantly influenced PAH levels. Melymuk et al. (Melymuk et al., 2016) examined the distribution of semi volatile organic compounds (SVOCs) in different indoor matrices within a residential environment. The study showed that airborne SVOC concentrations can be estimated from dust and surface concentrations, while compounds like PAHs require direct measurement due to ongoing primary emissions. Simonetti et al. (Simonetti et al., 2020) focused on the occurrence of halogenated pollutants in indoor dust from homes and workplaces in Italy. The study revealed higher concentrations of these pollutants in electrotechnical, and mechanical workshops compared to homes and offices. The study highlighted the importance of monitoring both domestic and occupational settings for comprehensive exposure assessment.

3.2.2. PAH concentration in air in houses

In comparing PAHs measured in homes, it is important to note that different studies employed various methodologies, making direct comparisons challenging. For instance, some studies measured PAHs in $PM_{2.5}$, other studies focused on PM_{10} . Additionally, certain studies reported the sum of gaseous PAHs and PM-bound PAHs, providing a more comprehensive picture of the total PAH burden but complicating direct comparisons with studies measuring only particulate-bound PAHs. To address these differences, this review categorizes the findings based on the measurement method and discusses them within these contexts. While quantitative comparisons are limited due to methodological variations, qualitative assessments can still provide valuable information about the trends and patterns of PAH concentrations in residential environments. Table S2 in Supplementary materials summarize the concentrations of indoor PAHs in house environments across several studies. Choi and Spengler (Choi & Spengler, 2014) reported concentrations of PAHs in $PM_{2.5}$ Poland, with a total of 6.37 ng/m^3 of seven measured PAHs. They found significant contributions of ambient sources to indoor PAH levels, especially in non-smoking homes, whereas indoor smoking notably increased PAH levels. Alves et al. (Alves et al., 2020) also measured PAHs concentrations in $PM_{2.5}$ in Portugal, and reported lower concentrations for most PAHs, such as BaP at 0.41 ng/m^3 and benzo[b]fluoranthene (BbF) at 0.53 ng/m^3 , with a total of 5.53 ng/m^3 for 13 measured PAHs. Rybak et al. (Rybak et al., 2019) observed a total concentration of 31.51 ng/m^3 in Poland. This study measured 15 PAHs using spider webs prepared in the laboratory and exposed to indoor air pollution, considering variables such as location, type of room, inhabitants' habits, and heating devices. Gustafson et al. (Gustafson et al., 2008) measured gaseous and PM-bound PAHs in Sweden, reporting moderate levels, such as Pyr at 1.72 ng/m^3 and fluoranthene (Flu) at 2.2 ng/m^3 . They reported significantly higher PAH levels in homes using wood-burning appliances, raising concerns about the associated health risks. Gaseous and PM-bound PAHs were

also measured in Loive et al. (Loive et al., 2024) in Sweden with a wide range of concentrations for some PAHs, such as BaP ranging from 0.01 to 0.85 ng/m³ and Flu ranging from 0.25 to 81 ng/m³, showing the variability in indoor PAH levels. De Genaro et al. (De Gennaro et al., 2015) in Italy measured concentrations of PAHs in PM₁₀, with BaA at 18.96 ng/m³ and benzo[g,h,i]perylene (BghiP) at 12.42 ng/m³. The concentrations were high in homes with wood stoves, emphasizing the impact of biomass combustion on IAQ.

3.2.3. PAH concentrations in air in schools

Table S2 in Supplementary materials presents the concentrations of various PAHs in the indoor air of schools from multiple studies, showing significant variation across different regions. As well as in measurements in houses, different studies employed various methodologies, making direct comparisons of the studies challenging. Lim et al. (Lim et al., 2021) from Sweden reported PAH concentrations in PM₁₀, with individual PAHs ranging from 0.002 ng/m³ for DahA to 0.021 ng/m³ for Flu. Rogula-Kozłowska et al. (Rogula-Kozłowska et al., 2018) from Poland showed a total PAH concentration of 16.1 ng/m³, with individual levels from 0.25 ng/m³ for DahA to 2.38 ng/m³ for BaP measured in PM₁. Romagnoli et al. (Romagnoli et al., 2016) from Italy reported concentrations in PM_{2.5} with a total of 2.79 ng/m³, where individual PAHs range from 0.05 ng/m³ for DahA to 0.5 ng/m³ for BbF. PAHs in PM_{2.5} were also measured in Błaszczuk et al. (Błaszczuk et al., 2017) from Poland with a total concentration of 33.75 ng/m³, and individual PAHs ranging from 0.4 ng/m³ for DahA to 3.65 ng/m³ for BghiP. Oliveira et al. (Oliveira et al., 2015) from Portugal indicated a total gaseous and PM-bound PAH concentration of 35.78 ng/m³, with individual levels from 0.13 ng/m³ for BaA to 1.9 ng/m³ for DahA. Additional context includes measured SUM of PAHs in Cirillo et al. (Cirillo et al., 2006) from Italy with 1.9 ng/m³ for gaseous PAHs, and for PM-bound PAHs in Fiala et al. (Fiala et al., 2001) from the Czech Republic with 7.04 ng/m³, Mortamais et al. (Mortamais et al., 2017) from Spain with 1107 pg/m³, and Van Drooge et al. (Van Drooge et al., 2020) from Spain with 500-3900 pg/m³.

Lim et al. (Lim et al., 2021) investigated PAHs in Stockholm preschools, finding significant correlations between outdoor and indoor PM₁₀ levels, with vehicle emissions and biomass burning as main sources. Rogula-Kozłowska et al. (Rogula-Kozłowska et al., 2018) studied PAH concentrations in teaching rooms in Poland, and noted higher outdoor concentrations and a potential unidentified indoor source of gaseous PAHs in Warsaw. Romagnoli et al. (Romagnoli et al., 2016) assessed air quality in various microenvironments in Rome, and identified motor vehicles, biomass burning, and soil resuspension as primary PAH sources. Oliveira et al. (Oliveira et al., 2015) focused on a preschool in Portugal, emphasizing the predominance of gaseous PAHs and the significant impact of outdoor emissions on indoor air quality. Błaszczuk et al. (Błaszczuk, Rogula-Kozłowska, 2017) examined PM_{2.5}-bound PAHs in Polish kindergartens, and reported high levels of PM_{2.5} and PAHs both indoors and outdoors, with solid fuel combustion identified as a significant source. Cirillo et al. (Cirillo et al., 2006) focused on multi-pathway exposure to PAHs among children in urban and rural areas of Campania, Italy, and highlighted that food was the primary source of PAH exposure. Fiala et al. (Fiala et al., 2001) assessed PAH intake in children in a Czech city, and found that food consumption was a more significant contributor to PAH exposure than air inhalation or soil ingestion. Mortamais et al. (Mortamais et al., 2017) investigated the association between PAH exposure and ADHD (Attention-deficit hyperactivity disorder) symptoms in children in Barcelona, Spain, and noted a significant link between PAH levels and changes in brain structures, although behavioural effects were not identified. Van Drooge et al. (Van Drooge et al., 2020) analysed PM_{2.5} aerosols in Barcelona primary schools, and identified traffic emissions as the primary source of PAHs in both indoor and outdoor environments. The concentrations were higher in schools located in high-traffic areas, with a significant transfer of outdoor pollutants to indoor air.

Figure 7. Differences in concentration of PAHs in PM_{2.5} in houses and schools

Figure 7 compares the concentrations of PM_{2.5}-bound PAHs between houses and schools. The results show that schools have significantly higher concentrations of PAHs compared to houses for most of the compounds. Specifically, the concentrations of BaA, Pyr, BbF and BghiP are notably higher in schools. In contrast, the concentration of IP is higher in houses than in schools. Other PAHs such as BaP, BkF and DahA also shows higher concentrations in schools, but the differences are less pronounced compared to others.

4. Conclusion

The analysis of VOC and PAH concentrations in various indoor environments, such as homes, schools, and offices, reveals their widespread presence and highlights the health impacts of these pollutants. VOCs, originating from sources like cleaning products, building materials, and daily activities, consistently show higher concentrations indoors, particularly in schools and homes where children spend most of their times. Studies from Italy, Poland, and Portugal indicate prevalent indoor VOCs such as benzene, toluene, ethylbenzene, xylenes, and formaldehyde, highlighting the need for improved ventilation, low-emission materials, and regular air quality monitoring to mitigate respiratory issues and long-term health effects. Similarly, PAHs primarily originating from traffic emissions, biomass burning, and indoor activities like smoking and cooking, have been detected at concerning levels in homes and schools, posing genotoxic risks and connection to health hazards. Research from Sweden, Poland, and Italy shows that indoor PAH levels often correlate with ambient air pollution but are also influenced by potential indoor sources, suggesting mitigation strategies focusing on reducing outdoor emissions, enhancing indoor ventilation, regular cleaning, and carefully selecting household products. Overall, the combined analysis of VOCs and PAHs emphasizes the need for comprehensive air quality management, including improved ventilation, use of low-emission materials, regular monitoring, traffic, and emission control, and public awareness to protect public health, particularly for vulnerable populations, such as children, the elderly and patients with existing chronic conditions. Comparing studies on indoor pollutants such as VOCs and PAHs was challenging due to the lack of standardized regulations and methodologies for measuring indoor air quality across different regions, particularly within the European Union. The inconsistencies in measurement protocols, sampling

techniques, analytical methods, and measurement units make it difficult to directly compare data and draw comprehensive conclusions. Moreover, the variability in building types, usage patterns, occupant behaviours, and climatic conditions further complicates the comparison. Studies often focus on different sets of pollutants, use varied durations for sampling, and apply distinct analytical techniques, resulting in discrepancies that hinder a unified understanding of indoor air quality issues. This highlights the urgent need for unique guidelines and standardized measurement practices to enable more reliable and comparable assessments of indoor air pollutants, facilitating more effective policy-making and public health interventions across Europe.

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